

ISic0393

I.Sicily inscription 0393

Language

Latin and Ancient Greek

Type

(?)

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI140830

1. [— — — — —]V V V . [— — — — —]
2. [— — — — —]AREI.INQVFREIVS.#⁷ [— — —]
3. [— — ἀμερίμ]ν[ι], οὐδὶς ἀθά[ν]α[τος].
- 4.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 491604

EDCS 21900433

PHI 140830

Bibliography

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